

Parallel Photon Mapping Computations to Enable Fast Approximate Solutions to the Art Gallery and Watchman Route Problems

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Abstract— The art gallery and watchman route problems (AGP and WRP) are NP-hard constrained optimization problems concerned with providing static and dynamic sensing, respectively, to environments such that the maximum amount of information is sensed at a minimal cost. What being an NP-hard problem means, practically, is that when an AGP or WRP solution is calculated for a particular time step t , any small change in the environment requires that an entirely new solution must be computed. Extending 3D AGP- and WRP-solving computations into 4D (i.e. considering time's effects on the solutions generated) means that a large number of computational resources would be consumed if the updates to the AGP and WRP solutions are performed serially - since each time step's solution would be computed sequentially. Our particular AGP- and WRP-solving algorithms are built upon the photon mapping algorithm in order to model the information obtainable in the sensed environment. The photon mapping algorithm models the propagation of multispectral photons through an environment and stores the result of the photons' interaction with their environment in a k-d tree data structure called a *photon map*. Since each virtual photon can operate independently of every other virtual photon, a photon map generated at a particular time step t can be generated independently of every other photon map populated at every other time step using a graphics processing unit (GPU). Thus given an n -sized time sequence, a photon map can be populated by each member of an n -core GPU. Once the photon map is updated, our AGP/WRP-solving algorithms can be executed in parallel over the time sequence using the particular core assigned to a photon map's population. We present the results of our computations and compare both serial- and GPU-based performance.

Keywords—route optimization; sensor placement optimization; photon mapping; GPU programming

I. INTRODUCTION

The *knowledge representation problem* is one of the fundamental challenges facing researchers attempting to construct autonomous vehicle path planning algorithms [1]. This problem states, in essence, that in order for interactive agents to conduct reasoning of the environment they are operating in, a computable model of that environment must be available. Most representations of the environment for which interactive agents are intended to operate within are

abstractions or *micro-worlds* which ignore some aspect of the real world in favor of computational tractability [2].

Of course, in the real world, interactive autonomous agents can confront environments which are poorly known and uncertain. Poorly known environments can be defined as lacking information to be utilized by the decision-making capabilities of interactive agents operating within a given environment. Uncertain environments can be defined as being subject to unpredictable changes which can disrupt the interactive agents' ability to complete their respective tasks. The major question facing autonomy researchers is how to computationally represent poorly known and uncertain environments in a physics-accurate way in order to be able to quickly adapt the interactive agents' mission plan(s) either in reaction to or in anticipation of such environments.

Photons represent quanta of information which interact with the material properties of the items occupying their world. When a photon is sensed, the information provided by a photon is conveyed to the sensors designed to capture it. Hence, we assert that knowledge representation can be achieved by modeling the propagation of photons. Modeling photons can be achieved by means of a graphics rendering technique known as photon mapping [3]. The outcome of this photon modeling algorithm is the production of a 3D queryable data structure –based upon a k-d tree - known as a *photon map*.

The photon map may be regarded as a surjective function whose domain is a set of tuples of the form (p, r, t) and whose range is a subset of \mathfrak{R}^3 . The value of p is the 3D position an autonomous agent happens to occupy at time t and r is the radius of the sphere surrounding the agent at position p . This tuple serves as a query to the photon map. (Note that r need not encompass a sphere. The spherical sensing volume in question could in fact be carved into any arbitrarily-shaped volume that admits photons on an arbitrary side.) The value returned by a query to the photon map is a set of points within the sphere defined by radius r that indicates the location of where photons have settled in the environment affected at time t by a(n) (attenuated) photon source.

The AGP [4] is an optimization problem that seeks to use the minimum number of sensors necessary to assure that every

point in the sensed space is covered by at least one sensor. The watchman route problem (WRP) [4] is closely related to the art gallery problem. The WRP is an optimization problem that seeks to use the minimum distance for an observer to trace through space such that every point in that space is sensed.

Let D be a set of points which comprise a surface and let it be a member of the compact subset Ω of \mathfrak{R}^d where \mathfrak{R}^d is a d -dimensional subset of the real numbers and $d \geq 2$. More formal definitions of the AGP and WRP are posited as the following questions:

- What is the minimum number of sensors necessary to ensure that the maximum number of elements of Ω are sensed [4]?
- What is the shortest route available such that the maximum number of elements of Ω are sensed [4]?

In our particular case, we represent the elements to be sensed in Ω as a collection of photons stored within a photon map. Our goal therefore is to construct algorithms that will sense the maximum number of elements of Ω while minimizing the number of resources necessary to perform that sensing.

Given a model of the environment represented by the photon map, the question becomes where to place static and mobile sensors such that they can capture the maximum number of photons via queries while minimizing the cost (however that is defined) of capturing the information they represent. A more robust solution to the AGP and WRP should also take into account less-than-ideal circumstances in a 3D virtual environment that can change over time. Furthermore, it is important to be able to adapt and alter the photon map over a sequence of time steps in order to subsequently alter and adapt the solutions produced for the AGP and WRP in order to accommodate these changes.

It has been shown that the photon mapping algorithm is amenable to real time updates via GPU processing. Such updates have been utilized by the game and simulation industry in order to provide incredibly realistic renderings of virtual environments. What this paper strives to achieve is to describe the GPU-based Optimized-Route eNginE (GORN) algorithm and how we can utilize these real time update technologies to photon maps to provide fast solutions to the AGP and WRP.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section II, we discuss previous AGP and WRP solution methods and discuss the nature of the photon mapping algorithm's ability to be updated in real time; in Section III we discuss how these realtime updates are used to provide quick solutions to the AGP and WRP; in Section IV we provide our results of this application; in Section V, we provide our conclusions and directions where we may pursue this research further.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Producing Real Time Updates to the Photon Map

Modeling the behavior of photons within a graphics rendering context was introduced in [8]. Jensen introduced the popular two-pass algorithm used today in [9]. This paper treated

illumination and visibility into two different domains. Light particles are propagated and their visibility to an observer is established by querying a k - d tree. An image is produced by tracing a ray from a camera stationed within the scene and then gathering nearby photons where the ray intersects the scene.

The first GPU-based implementation of photon mapping was introduced in [10]. The virtual photons' propagation was stored in a regular grid using a technique called stencil routing. The paper [11] augmented the work of [10] by performing hemi-cube final ray tracing to produce an image – this technique was similar to techniques used to produce hardware accelerated radiosity. The paper [7] dealt specifically with the hardware acceleration of the creation and updating of the k - d tree that utilized a greedy parallel technique for adding photons. The efforts used in our paper are inspired and based upon the GPU-accelerated photon mapping techniques introduced in [12] and will be discussed in greater detail in the Section III below.

B. Using the Photon Map to Produce Solutions to the AGP and WRP

The original art gallery theorem was developed from the study of two dimensional polygons which provide a sufficient number of stationary observers needed to sufficiently guard the polygonal area. For a general polytope with n vertices, $\lfloor n/3 \rfloor$ stationary observers are necessary and sufficient, but for n -vertices orthogonal polytopes, the number of stationary observers is reduced to $\lfloor n/4 \rfloor$ [13].

The result of the AGP is also extendable to mobile observer provided tractable restrictions are applied as in the case of our problem. Mobile observers required fewer observers than the stationary observers. For sufficient condition, only $\lfloor n/4 \rfloor$ mobile observers are needed to an n vertex polytope.

Solutions to the WRP are usually focused on the visibility properties of a route. The problem to be solved is to find the shortest route from a point s back to itself with the property that each point in a given space is visible from at least one point along the route. Usually the WRP yield a unique route in a simple polygon, except for case where there is an infinite number of different shortest routes of equal length [14].

Well-known variants of the WRP include Safari and Zookeeper Route Problem. The general problem of WRP published in the literature mostly about simple polygons and convex polygon. If the starting point of the route is known or given, then the problem is refers to as fixed WRP. Otherwise it is refers to as floating WRP.

Consideration of how to provide a solution to the WRP relied upon solving the AGP and then using a traveling salesman problem (TSP) solver to connect the AGP-solving waypoints within the environment. In [15] their WRP-solution was applied to the inspection of a ship's hull. The paper [16] further refined the work in [15] by offering a shorter, smoother WRP solution which took into account differential environmental changes in the TSP route edges. The efforts made in [17] built upon the work of [18] but with the application of a k - d tree (though it was not populated by a

photon mapping algorithm) to make quick AGP-solving sensor coverage queries towards the ultimate goal of solving the WRP using a TSP solver.

As mentioned above, the factor that made Jensen's work on photon mapping so popular was the distinction made between the virtual photons' ability to illuminate a scene and their visibility. Capitalizing on this distinction, the papers [19], [20] and [21] have utilized the query step as a means of determining the visibility obtainable by the photons stored in the k-d tree resulting from the photons' propagation. This query serves as a means of filling a level set at time t which are then used by algorithms mentioned in [19] and [21] to solve the AGP and WRP respectively. The spherical-shaped query (or *query-sphere*) of radius r centered at point x_o (or *query-point*) is performed in order to provides the best information available at time t to the observer in an uncertain and changing environment. Our WRP- and AGP-solving goals are achieved when we optimize the performance of the observer such that it will capture the greatest number of photons not shared by any other observer while minimizing the path length required capturing them.

II. METHODS

A. Creating and Partitioning the Observer Grid

In order for our photon mapping-mediated AGP and WRP solutions to be successful, we must achieve three goals, namely:

1. Creating and partitioning our observer grid, and
2. Incorporating photon mapping into our observer grid,

With regard to item 1, let O be a set of points which comprises a surface of a model within the virtual environment and let it be a member of the compact subset $\Omega \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^d$ where $d \geq 2$. The set O contains those objects which obstruct visibility - or *occluders* - residing in environment Ω . The set $X = \Omega \setminus O$ is the set of points in which a (possibly) omnidirectional sensor may be stationed and $x_o \in X$ is some candidate sensor position. A UV-observer grid $G \subseteq X$ is comprised of a sequence of points g_0, g_1, \dots, g_n wherein element g_i is separated by its neighboring elements by some distance such that the distance does not exceed the boundaries of G . (This distance assumption ensures that at least one waypoint is found within the confines of G . In our application, we presume an equal geodesic distance of one separating points found in G .)

Our algorithm uses a 3D UV-observer grid. Hence, we will sometimes use the terminology $g_{i,j,k} \in G$ to indicate a grid point located i units on the x -axis, j units on the y -axis and k units on the z -axis. The position of grid element $g_r \in G$ is found by letting $r = i + j \cdot n_x + k \cdot (n_x n_y)$ where n_x and n_y are the total number of grid points found on the x and y -axes, respectively. Note that elements of the UV-observer grid G may be discarded or added according to some criteria.

With regard to item 2, in order to incorporate photon mapping into our observer grid, we note that the photon map, being ultimately a 3D query-able k-d tree, may be queried at some point in space in G to yield a subset of the photons contained within it. The number of photons returned by the

photon map at a point in space within G represents the amount of illumination-energy present at that point and may be regarded as a scalar *photon volume*. (Conversely, if a point is not illuminated, it may be regarded as being *shadowed*.) Having a measurement of a point's photon volume provides us with the ability to create a gradient distinguishing between those points in a 3D virtual environment which are shadowed from those that are illuminated. Information concerning how to determine what photons are visible may be found in [3] and [19].

We will now review how to determine maximum non-overlapping visibility in either 2 or 3 dimensions. Given the grid points, g_0, g_1, \dots, g_n and the set of photon-illuminated points $y_0, y_1 \dots, y_p$ residing on the exterior surfaces of the occluders O , the establishment of visibility is a consequence of determining the amount of non-occluded space encompassed within the viewing area sensed by n sensors. This concept of finding the number of visible photons is expressed in the following equation inspired by [4]

$$V(g_0, g_1, \dots, g_n) = \sum_{k=0}^p H \left(\sum_{i=0}^n H(\Phi(y_k; g_i)) \right) \quad (1)$$

where $H(\bullet)$ is the one-dimensional Heaviside step function, with $H(0) = 0$ and $\Phi(y_k; g_i)$ is a level set producing a positive real number if a ray can be traced from photon position y_k to grid point g_i and a negative real number otherwise. The entire possible number of photons that can be sensed is

$$\sum_{k=0}^p H(\Psi(y_k)) \quad (2)$$

The normalized visible volume, V_{norm} , describes the fraction of coverage proved by the sensors and is provided by the following equation

$$V_{norm} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^p (\sum_{i=0}^n H(\Phi(y_k; x_i)))}{\sum_{k=0}^p H(\Psi(y_k))} \quad (3)$$

and $0 \leq V_{norm} \leq 1$.

The method for establishing sensor placement in order to achieve maximum coverage is provided by the following equation:

$$\underset{g_j \in G}{argmax} \sum_{k=0}^p H \left(H(\Phi(y_k; g_j)) - H \left(\sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n H(\Phi(y_k; g_i)) \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

The first term gives the visible region provided by the j th sensor. The second term is the visible volume of photons

provided by all other sensors. The equation provides an exhaustive search of the optimal location for one sensor at a time. The algorithm used to generate maximum non-overlapping visibility is called Sensor Placement Optimization via Queries or SPOQ and is detailed further in [19].

Once this approximately optimal AGP-solving information is available, we treat the optimal route finding problem as a segmentation problem. We have taken two approaches to segmentation, namely, Chan-Vese [22] and k-means. Given an environment Ω populated with a set of UxV-observer grid points, G , illuminated by p photons, the SPOQ algorithm produces $j + 1$ grid points $\{g_0 \dots g_j\} \subset G$ which have the greatest visible photon volume sensed by an UxV stationed at a grid point $g \in \{g_0 \dots g_j\}$ such that the photons comprising the photon volume sensed at grid point g are *unique* – that is to say, no element in $\{g_0 \dots g_j\} \setminus \{g\}$ senses the same photons as those found at g .

The initial segmentation curve is created by connecting the grid points comprising $\{g_0 \dots g_j\}$ by some means such that they form a closed curve. Note that if our WRP-solving route contains the waypoints solving the AGP, we can then be assured that it contains the maximum number of uniquely-sensed photons obtainable. The eventual construction of the minimum-energy segmentation mesh affords us a set of candidate waypoints that, when connected, provide a greater photon volume than waypoints not within the mesh.

Let $\phi_{i,j,k}^n$ denote the value of the evolving Chan-Vese segmentation curve applied to G at grid point $g_{i,j,k}$ at an iterative step n . Once the SPOQ-mediated initialization has been completed and the initial segmentation curve - $\phi_{i,j,k}^0$ - has been produced, the following iterative solution to the Chan-Vese segmentation algorithm is applied to yield $\phi_{i,j,k}^{n+1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{i,j,k}^{n+1} = & F_1 \phi_{i+1,j,k}^{n+1} + F_2 \phi_{i-1,j,k}^{n+1} + F_3 \phi_{i,j+1,k}^{n+1} + \\ & F_4 \phi_{i,j-1,k}^{n+1} + F_5 \phi_{i,j,k+1}^{n+1} + F_6 \phi_{i,j,k-1}^{n+1} + \\ & F w_{i,j,k} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$F_l = \frac{\Delta t \delta_h \left(\phi_{i,j,k}^n \right) \mu (p \cdot L(\phi^n)^{p-1}) C_l}{h + \Delta t \delta_h \left(\phi_{i,j,k}^n \right) \mu (p \cdot L(\phi^n)^{p-1}) (\sum_{g=1}^6 C_g)} \quad (6)$$

for $l = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$, and

$$F = \frac{h}{h + \Delta t \delta_h \left(\phi_{i,j,k}^n \right) \mu (p \cdot L(\phi^n)^{p-1}) (\sum_{g=1}^6 C_g)} \quad (7)$$

and the error factor $w_{i,j,k}$ is

$$w_{i,j,k} = \phi_{i,j,k}^n - \Delta t \delta_h \left(\phi_{i,j,k}^n \right) \left(\nu \lambda_1 \left(G_{i,j,k}^v - c_1(\phi^n) \right)^2 - \lambda_2 \left(G_{i,j,k}^v - c_2(\phi^n) \right)^2 \right) \quad (8)$$

The variables C_g and C_l conform to a pattern explained in

[20]. The parameters μ , ν , λ_1 , λ_2 and b may be arbitrarily defined. (Chan and Vese set $\nu = 0$, and $b = 1$, $\lambda_1 = 1$, $\lambda_2 = 1$ [22], we do something similar). Given a smooth approximation of the Heaviside function $H(\phi)$, the values of c_1 and c_2 are the region averages of G in the respective regions where $\phi \geq 0$ and $\phi < 0$.

The variable $L(\phi^n)$ is the surface area of the segmentation mesh and the formula for its calculation is:

$$L(\phi^n) = \int_G \delta_h(\phi^n) |\nabla \phi^n| dx dy dz. \quad (9)$$

The delta function δ_h serves to smooth the segmentation mesh as it evolves. For details regarding its calculation, please refer to [23]. The von Neumann boundary conditions apply to Eq. 5 as described in [22].

The algorithm used to generate maximum non-overlapping visibility is called the Photon-mapping-Informed active-Contour Route Designator or PICRD. The name derives from the fact that we are using a photon-mapping-informed PDE-based active contour segmentation algorithm to allow us to designate a shortest-path route through the high-visibility vertices comprising the 3D mesh produced within our 3D virtual environment and is detailed further in [21].

As an alternative to the Chan-Vese algorithm we also used a k -means classifier arriving from the ITK computer vision toolkit [24] that clusters around grid points with higher and lower photon volumes chosen by our SPOQ algorithm. The elements that k -means operates on consists of an array of size $|G|$ wherein the i th element corresponds to element $g_i \in G$ and that element's value is g_i 's photon volume. (The initial mean value of the cluster of high-photon-volume grid points arrives from the photon volume of those points used as the initial condition to the Chan-Vese algorithm.)

Once we have our observation grid, incorporated photon mapping and have approximately optimal solutions to the AGP and WRP, we can then apply our GPU-based optimization for finding solutions to the AGP and WRP.

B. GPU-based Photon Mapping

The software that we used as the foundation of our GPU-based photon mapping computations was the Opposite Renderer [12] based on C++ and Qt [25]. The Opposite Renderer engine is implemented using the 3.0 version of the OptiX framework [26]. The OptiX SDK photon mapping algorithm was modified for a GPU for the purposes of this renderers' functionality. Using the photon mapping source code provided by this renderer, we adapted it for our purposes of providing accelerated GPU computations. Once the photon mapping updates were performed, we fed the results to our AGP/WRP solving algorithms and then visualized the results with an offline renderer.

C. Zeno's Paradox

The important thing to note about the AGP and WRP is that they are in the family of NP-hard problems [5]. What this means, practically, is that when a WRP solution is calculated

for a particular time step t , any small change in the environment requires that an entirely new approximate AGP and WRP solution must be computed. So, when considering the problem of extending 3D AGP and WRP computations into 4D (i.e. considering time's effects on the environment explored by the watchman) a large number of computational resources would be consumed if the updates to the AGP's and WRP's approximate solution were performed serially since each time step would have to be computed sequentially.

The key to the success of our algorithm can be expressed with Zeno's Paradox [27] namely: "If everything when it occupies an equal space is at rest, and if that which is in locomotion is always occupying such a space at any moment, the flying arrow is therefore motionless." What this means in our context is that miniscule changes in a covered area do not require drastic alterations in the candidate AGP-solving sensor positions that were originally chosen. Using this heuristic rule and after establishing an initial set of candidate sensor points, we can simply query a set of neighboring candidate sensor positions rather than the entire sensor grid. Thus, we can circumvent the small memory space provided by GPUs and focus on updates that occur within a miniscule time update.

A drawback to our approach is that once we have established the best candidate sensor positions providing the best non-overlapping coverage for a fixed number of sensors (in our experiments we used 3 sensors) we cannot alter that number without recalculating the entire solution once again because the expansion or contraction of the number of sensors would therefore introduce the possibility of providing either less than optimal coverage or greater but overlapping coverage, respectively.

D. Combining Concepts

The result of applying our simulation's approximately optimal AGP solver is the sequence S , consisting of subsequences $s_0 \dots s_n$ corresponding to time steps $t_0 \dots t_n$ indicating the best candidate waypoint positions for obtaining the maximum amount of information while using the smallest number of waypoints available. The waypoints connecting the approximately optimal AGP-solving points are then chosen using a k -means algorithm to allow for further speedup. Subsequences can be partitioned and distributed to individual members of the teams when the information content is best gathered in the air, underwater or on the water's surface. At each element of the sequence S , small changes are applied to the covered space and then a query is made to the GPU-enhanced photon map generation algorithm.

Obviously, a purely random set of candidate waypoints would not be very practical for a determining where to place a sensor because there's no guarantee that candidate waypoints would neighbor a particular candidate sensor position. Hence, the 3D grid G contains waypoints that are regularly distributed and having an arbitrary granularity in order to fill the sensed area's space.

When establishing the paths between AGP-solving waypoints as a precursor to solving the WRP, we utilize Dijkstra's shortest path finding algorithm in order to allow greater adaptability since Dijkstra's algorithm concerns itself

with finding a short path between two waypoints. Hence if there is no change in the established AGP-solving sensor positions (due to our minimal change Zeno's Paradox inspired heuristic) we may therefore ignore computing paths for waypoints that have not been altered.

III. THE GORN ALGORITHM

Using photon-mapping as a means of informing the Chan-Vese and k -means segmentation algorithm allows for the accommodation of scenes which may also be affected by information-attenuating events such as participating media, low-illumination conditions and possible moving obstacles.

The name we give to our heuristic WRP-solving algorithm is the Photon-mapping-Informed active-Contour Route Designator or PICRD [21]. The name derives from the fact that we are using a photon-mapping-informed PDE-based active contour segmentation algorithm to allow us to designate a shortest-path route through the high-visibility vertices comprising the 3D mesh produced within our 3D virtual environment

Combining the steps considered previously, the complete GORN algorithm is given below. See Section IV for the assumptions used for our algorithm.

Algorithm 1 GORN

1. Construct a 3D model of the virtual environment using some modeling toolkit.
2. Construct the observer grid G
3. Introduce participating media
4. Apply the GPU-enhanced photon mapping algorithm to the virtual environment
5. Obtain the photon volume at every grid point $g_i \in G$
6. Solve the AGP for subsequence $s_i \in S$ using the SPOQ algorithm
7. Apply the 3D photon-mapping-informed Chan-Vese segmentation algorithm or k -means algorithm
8. Connect the AGP-solving observer grid points established in Step 6 using shortest path-finding algorithm while using the segmentation-mesh vertices produced by Step 7 as waypoints.
9. Alter the environment according to some criteria such as varying the amount of illumination present.
10. Choose a set of neighbors surrounding SPOQ-generated sensor candidates in time step t_{n-1}
11. Repeat steps 4 – 10 for time steps $t_1 \dots t_n$.

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A. An Application Scenario

When performing our experiments listed below, we make the following assumptions:

1. The photons are confined to the visible light spectrum.
2. The shortest-path-finding algorithm used to connect our AGP-solving points is Dijkstra’s algorithm [27].
3. The sensors used are omnidirectional with a range of one third the length of the model on the z -axis.
4. Only 3 observers are used and maintained for SPOQ.

Within the context of our simulation scenario, we applied GORN to the following simple cityscape model.

1. Using 1020 grid points and 2500, 5000 and 7500 photons cast using GORN and serial processing, and
2. Using 6897 grid points and 2500, 5000 and 7500 photons cast using GORN and serial processing.

The first scenario may be regarded as a means of testing GORN with gradually increasing “brightness” in terms of photons launched, the second scenario represents the scalability of the GORN algorithm when applied to larger grids. In each instance, the results from the GORN algorithm were compared to a non-GPU-based serial application of the above algorithms.

V. RESULTS

Figure 1 depicts the AGP- and WRP-solving observation positions (given in red) generated at time step t_0 .

Fig. 1. The initial AGP-solving positions in the virtual environment

The tables below show the results of applying GORN and a non-GPU-based algorithm (designated “Serial”) to scenarios 1, 2, and 3. Note that the column indicating a percentage of uniquely sensed photons represents the coverage obtained as a percentage of the total number of photons available to be

sensed. The subsequent column measures coverage in terms of the photon volume sensed as the shortest route is traversed. The path distance is the number of edges connecting the vertices together. Recall that we assign a distance of one to each edge in the segmentation mesh. Note that each time generated arrives after the initial condition is met. (The initial step takes approximately 3 times longer.)

TABLE I Result of Using GORN in Scenario 1			
Path Finding Algorithm	% of Uniquely-Sensed Photons	Path Distance	Time Required (ms)
Photons Launched: 2500			
GORN	94.4	18	32
Serial	93.2	18	82
Photons Launched: 5000			
GORN	95.2	19	34
Serial	93.9	19	85
Photons Launched: 7500			
GORN	96.1	15	36
Serial	95.2	19	84

TABLE II Result of Using GORN in Scenario 2			
Path Finding Algorithm	% of Uniquely-Sensed Photons	Path Distance	Time Required (ms)
Photons Launched: 2500			
GORN	94.1	32	33
Serial	94.2	33	83
Photons Launched: 5000			
GORN	95.6	35	34
Serial	95.5	34	82
Photons Launched: 7500			
GORN	96.3	37	36
Serial	96.2	36	86

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

We can see the benefits which accrue from the decoupling of the visibility calculation and the update of the k - d tree responsible for providing that visibility. This result can be expected since the algorithm constitutes a “pleasantly parallel” algorithm wherein each subsequence of potential waypoints can operate independently of another subsequence.

One area we would like to explore to improve our algorithm further would be incorporating multi-spectral photons in a manner similar to that described in [28].

There are many potential applications for this algorithm. One possible application is the provision of tactical adaptability to autonomous vehicles encountering rapidly changing environments.

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